

Effect of deposition position on microstructure of HfC coating fabricated by low pressure chemical vapor deposition

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1. Introduction

As ablation resistance material, C/C composites have unmatched properties compared with the others, such as the low density, low CTE (coefficient of thermal expansion) and their higher thermal strength even above 2000 °C; So the composites have become the ideal option for the nose cone and leading edge at supersonic aircraft^[1,2]. However, the C/C composites are very apt to be oxidized at high temperature. Aiming to this, many Si-based ceramic coating systems were developed and can protect the composites for long time under 1700 °C^[3]. But, for the oxidation and ablation resistance at higher temperature, especially under the particles flow with high speed, these coating become disabled. So, the carbides with higher melting point should be introduced into the coating in order to improve the resistance ability at high temperature^[4], such as HfC, TaC^[5], NbC, ZrC^[6,7] et al; and among these, HfC has the highest melting point of 3890 °C, and relative better thermal stability, therefore, it becomes the ideal coating material for the ablation resistance for supersonic fly.

Compared with the other methods (sol-gel^[8], plasma spraying^[9]), HfC coating obtained through chemical vapor deposition has more dense structure and better design ability, so the CVD method is always firstly adopted when a multilayer system is needed. However, the HfC microstructure is sensitive with the deposition craft, and HfCl₄, the solid precursor of Hf, is hard to be well controlled. So, to get a coating with a better ablation resistance, the rules between microstructure and deposition craft should be well studied. Up to now, rare reports can be found about the HfC coating prepared by CVD.

In this paper, HfC coating was prepared on the surface of the C/C composites, and the effect of deposition position on the microstructure of the HfC coating was studied.

2. Experimental

2.1 Experiment materials

Small specimens (50mm×10mm×3mm) used as the substrates were cut from bulk 2-D C/C composites with a density of 1.71g/cm³. These specimens were hand-polished using 400 grit SiC paper, then cleaned with distilled water and dried at 393K for 2 h.

HfCl₄ (Alfa Aesar, 99.9%) and C₃H₆ (>99.9%) were used as the precursor of Hf and C. The Ar and H₂ used in the deposition are both high purity (>99.999%).

2.2 Preparation of HfC coating

The as-prepared C/C samples were hanged with carbon fiber in the reaction chamber equidistantly, from 15cm to 30 cm away from the gas inlet. And the samples were labeled **a**, **b**, **c**, **d** respectively, as seen in the Fig. 1.

The deposition was carried out in a two-temperature zone CVD furnace. The HfCl₄ vapor was produced by heating HfCl₄ powder at lower temperature zone of the furnace, with H₂ being the carrier gas. All the gases were mixed in the gas mixer at before injected into high temperature reaction chamber. The reaction of HfC deposition process can be prescribed by the formula 1, as follow:

2.3 Test methods

The grown morphology was observed through Field emission scanning electron microscope (Supera-55); the phase constitution was examined by X-ray diffraction (Rigaku-D/max-3C).

According to the results of XRD patterns, the texture coefficients of different crystal plane were also calculated through Harris's method. Meanwhile, the grown orientation at different position was analyzed by the changes of the TC; the formula used was presented as follow [10, 7]:

$$TC = \frac{I_i / I_0}{(1/n) \times \sum_{i=1}^n (I_i / I_0)} \quad (2)$$

TC: the texture coefficient of one plane;
 I_i : the intensity of crystal plane as detected;
 I_0 : the intensity of crystal plane in the standard XRD pattern from ASTM (American Society for Testing Materials Index);
 n : numbers of the crystal planes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Phase composition of HfC coating

From Fig 2, it can be seen that the HfC coating has single phase composition at position **a**. No peaks of C phase were detected. With the position lifting, weak peaks of C appeared in the HfC coating at position **b**. At position **c**, the C peak intensity continued to increase; that is, it can be included that the C content increased with the position lifting. While at **d**, which is in the downstream of gas flow, the main peak of C became the strongest one, it is because that the C intensity mainly came from the matrix; in the downstream of gas flow, the deposition rate was too low to form a thick layer. The coating was too thin for the X-ray diffraction test, and the C of matrix can be easily detected.

Meanwhile, it is remarkable that the peaks of HfC appeared a certain shift to the left at position **a**. It is because that the Hf was excess relatively, HfC coating was apt to exist as carbon deficiency form: $HfC_{0.6-0.99}$, which is coincided with the normal existence of HfC in the form of metal excess [11].

Fig.3 shows the texture coefficient of HfC coating at different position, it can be found that with the position lifting, the TC of planes changes a lot. In the upstream of gas flow, (111) plane has the highest TC, the TC of (200) is the lowest. With the changes of position, TC of (111) plane decreases gradually, but the TC of (200) increases adversely. Slightly changes happened to the TC of (220) and (311) planes. It is can be illustrated that growth orientation of HfC coating transferred from (111) to (200), which can also be exhibited in the XRD patterns (Fig.2): the intensity's increase of the (111) and (222) peak, the decrease of the (200) and (400) peak intensity.

When the gas flow passed from inlet to outlet, the reactants were consumed gradually. So there will be great concentration diversity generated in parallel direction of the flow. In the upstream, the supersaturation of reactants' concentration was higher; the grown process exhibited high nucleation rate, no obvious preferred grown orientation appeared; while in the downstream, the supersaturation dropped tempestuously, and so did the nucleation rate. Therefore, the coating became to grow toward a preferred orientation: (220) plane.

3.2 Microstructure of HfC coating

The changes on the reactant concentration resulted in not only the grown orientation transformation, but also the morphology of the coating, as shown in Fig. 4. In position **a**, the surface is compact and flat, the grains are spherical with a large size. With the position lifting, the size of HfC grains decreased. The space among the grains enlarged obviously, the coating surface became to be rough. In the downstream, the grain size diminished continuously and presented "shadow effect" because of the so thin film caused by the low deposition rate.

When the reactants entered into the high-temperature zone, the deposition reaction started immediately; and with the consumption of $HfCl_4$, C_3H_6 , H_2 , the reactant concentration began to reduce. In the upstream, the concentration was higher than the other regions and behaved a higher nucleation rate, which was propitious for the grown up of the grains and the inosculation between them. Therefore, the grains looked big and little space among the

grains was found, so the coating exhibited compact and flat.

In the mid-position, the concentration was lower than that in upstream, the nucleation rate decreased. The grown up and inosulation effect of the grains weakened, so the space between grains enlarged and the size of grains began to decreased. The surface became to be rough and loosen.

In the downstream, the concentration of HfCl_4 , C_3H_6 and H_2 were very low. The deposition carried on so slow. After 4h deposition, the coating was still thin, just for several μm . So the HfC behaved "shadow effect", that is, the coating reflected the morphology of the matrix surface, just like the shadow of the composition surface.

3.3 deposition rate of HfC coating

Fig.5 and 6 show the deposition rate and the thickness of HfC coating at different position. It can be seen that the deposition rate decreased rapidly with the enlargement of the distance from inlet. In position **a**, for 4h deposition the coating had a thickness of $63.6\mu\text{m}$, deposition rate reached to $15.9\mu\text{m/h}$. the deposition became slower because of the consumption of the reactants. At position **d** of downstream, the deposition was so slow, the deposition rate was just $2.1\mu\text{m/h}$, and the coating thickness was less than $10\mu\text{m}$.

The slow down of HfC deposition rate can be explained by the concentration boundary model of CVD, as shown in Fig. 7^[12]. As prescribed in the Figure, the chemical vapor deposition can be divided into several processes:

- 1) the HfCl_4 , C_3H_6 and H_2 diffuse to the surface from the main gas flow and are absorbed on the surface;
- 2) the reactants begin to react on composition surface;
- 3) the unreacted gas and the reaction products desorbed from surface and diffuse into the main gas flow.

Among all the steps above, the slowest process determined the final deposition speed. With the reaction conditions in this paper, the mass transmission processes, that is, the diffusion processes, became the key control steps.

In upstream, there is great concentration gradient between the main gas flow and the reaction interface. The diffusion is more quickly than that in downstream. More reactants can be transformed to the reaction interface in the same period of time, which will drive the reaction to be act more quickly. During the gas passed to the outlet, the concentration decreased gradually, the diffusion became slower and slower, so did the reaction process. That is the reason of slow-down of the deposition rate.

4. Conclusion

- (1) At position **a** (15-20cm from the gas inlet), the as-prepared HfC coating has single phase composition. With the increase of the distance from inlet, the C peak became stronger, and the grown orientation transferred into (200) plane.
- (2) With the increase of the distance from inlet, HfC grains size decreased gradually, and the coating became to be rougher.
- (3) With the increase of the distance from inlet, the deposition rate decreased from $15.9\mu\text{m/h}$ to $2.1\mu\text{m/h}$.

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Fig. 1 The scheme of the samples position

Fig. 2 The XRD patterns of HfC coating at different position

Fig. 3 The texture coefficient of HfC coating at different position

Fig. 4 The surface SEM images of the HfC coatings at different position

Fig.5 The thickness of the HfC coating at different deposition position

Fig. 6 deposition rate of the HfC coating at different position

Fig.7 concentration boundary model of CVD